
Developing Insaniah Model of the at-Risk Youth into Agripreneur in Selected Vocational Colleges in Malaysia: A Systematic Literature Review

Nurul Azreen Binti Salleh¹

YM Prof Dr Hj Raja Suzana Binti Raja Kasim²

^{1,2}Faculty of Entrepreneurship and Business, Universiti Malaysia Kelantan, Malaysia

Correspondence email: azreensalleh@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

At-risk youths in this paper are students selected from troubled family backgrounds with low-income, and who may also often youth of abusive parents, and drug addicts. They appear to have low literacy as studies had cited an increase of involvement in gangs, which resulted in poor grades, absenteeism and drug abuse. The crime made by youth is the participation of illegal activities and form part of the issues. At such, building a value of Islamic lifestyle system is to position youth's a role in the society is critical to address problems among at-risk youth. The paper aims to offer a new set of an insaniah of Islam as a model for inclusivity of the at-risk youth that are currently studying at selected agriculture vocational colleges (TVET) in Malaysia by developing them with new skillsets in sustainable agriculture. In preparing at-risk youth in this category, the model may challenge the assumptions of how the contemporary education brings about a change to embrace Islam values with new opportunity in life and equipped them with agripreneurship education. The systematic literature review is employed in this paper among selected publications; Emerald Insights, Proquest Dissertation, Springerlink, Research Gate, Google Scholar, Sage Pub, Science and Direct Pro Quest which have produced 1,499 results from 2000 until 2019. Most of the empirical studies are based on quantitative research methods. The outcome offers a systematic analysis from research evidence on aspirational agriculture and the learning-by-doing in entrepreneurship education, numbers of areas that need further study. Lack of research had focused on insaniah value and learning-by-doing associating at-risk youth venture into agriculture as a career pathways.

Keywords: Entrepreneur; Agriculture Entrepreneur; Agriculture Aspiration; At-Risk Youth; Insaniah Model; Systematic Literature Review

INTRODUCTION

There is a potential gap in bridging the theory of change (Siti Hajar, Noralini, Abd Hadi, & Haris, 2012); Noraini, & Hasan, 2008) in the perspectives of delivering an insaniah value model into the agriculture entrepreneurship education while at the same time preparing future agripreneur for the vulnerable communities such as at-risk youth. At-risk youths in this paper are students

selected from troubled family backgrounds with low-income, and who may also often youth of abusive parents, and drug addicts (Azlina, 2010; Koh, 2009; Salman, Samsudin, & Yusuf, 2017; Chong, S.T., Choon, L.D.K., Ibrahim, F., Samsudin, A., 2017). They appear to have low literacy as studies had cited an increase of involvement in gangs, poor grades, absenteeism and drug abuse (Balan, Samsudin, Soon Singh, & Juliana, 2017). Education is particularly important here as it can help youth break the cycle that created their circumstances in the first place. In the human domain, insaniah model as defined in this study comprises of positive personal qualities for millennials with those emotional intelligence, mental resilience, and a sense of purpose needed going forward (Salman, Samsudin, & Yusuf, 2017; Nor Hafizah, Zaihairul & Geshina, 2012). At-risk youth as a vulnerable group and demands support in order to prepare their career in future agriculture.

As sixty percent of jobs hired in the next generation do not exist today; future agriculture is identified as one of the areas that new jobs will emerge (Salman, Samsudin, & Yusuf, 2017). Thus, instilling a sense of purpose for a lifelong journey requires quality insaniah values into agriculture entrepreneurship education so as to help structure at-risk youths' goals and define the steps toward it. Education is particularly important here as it can help youth break the cycle that created their circumstances in the first place. The crime made by youth is the participation of illegal activities. These unhealthy activities form part of the issues among the at-risk youth (Salman, Samsudin, & Yusuf, 2017). At such, building a value of Islamic lifestyle system in making Allah as the Greatest love, to be loved and to be feared, and making Him the driving force in serving and providing the utmost benefit to mankind will make them feel being attended, meaningful and have a role in the society.

Designing innovative insaniah model as solutions to cater the demand for the high value human potentials to deal with management of the agriculture products; requires a new model in research and resulting economic effects of the new agripreneur (Raja Suzana, Zulazli, & Zainudin, 2017). As such, the study aims to offer a new set of an insaniah of Islam as a model for inclusivity of the at-risk youth that are currently studying at selected agriculture vocational colleges (TVET) in Malaysia by developing them with new skillsets in sustainable agriculture.

Numerous past research derived from the western viewing the agripreneur development and future (Samsudin, & Hasan, 2017; Koh, 2009; Salman, et al., 2017; Chong, S.T., et al., 2017). Lack of research focusing on developing an insaniah value among learners of agripreneur (Chong, S.T., et al., 2017). Furthermore, youths appear to be more interested working in white-collar jobs. Career in agriculture was not a priority due to the 3D mentality (dirty, difficult and dangerous), lack of sustainability, low in profitability and in social status. With a target sample of at-risk youth in agriculture vocational colleges (AVC), it was found agriculture entrepreneurship was being taught directly or indirectly among these colleges. This paper aims to explore the extent of learning-by-doing in this agenda of building agripreneurs.

Learning-by-doing in entrepreneurship education and its intervention will be explored in the following aspects; firstly, the phases of building agripreneur in operational plan. Secondly, on the agriproduct description, and, thirdly on go-to-market analysis to co-develop funding and financing opportunities for agripreneur startup growth. According to Tranfield, Denyer, & Smart, (2003), systematic reviews are based on systematic methods and aim to collect, evaluate and synthesize all studies on the topic. This paper also identifies gaps in the literature to help further accumulate scientific knowledge.

Although it is complex and time consuming (Mills, Montori, Ross, Shea, Wilson, & Guyatt, 2005), systematic reviews play an important role in contributing to the academy of literature as

well as methodological advances for the field of study. Based on the issues and research problems identified in the systematic literature review concerning the presence *insaniah* values standard possess among the at-risk youth in Malaysia, the following three (3) research questions are established:

1. To determine the existing learning-by-doing in Entrepreneurship Education among selected agriculture vocational colleges in Malaysia;
2. To examine levels of *insaniah* value education being learnt among youth-at risk studying at selected agriculture vocational colleges in Malaysia; and
3. To develop an *insaniah* value model into the Agrobased TVETpreneurship Education Framework.

Thus, the following research questions are formulated:

1. What elements of learning-by-doing activities exist in the Entrepreneurship Education among selected Agriculture vocational colleges in Malaysia?
2. What levels of *insaniah* value education being learnt among youth-at risk studying at selected Agriculture vocational colleges in Malaysia?
3. What nature of *insaniah* value model can be developed into the Agrobased TVETpreneurship Education Framework?

This paper aims to construct a framework that synthesizes the sophistication of an easily accessible shared literature. It provides a basis for the study of the scaling mechanisms of initiatives starting from the bottom up by presenting the latest knowledge on the topic (what is known and where the gaps are) and by providing the conceptual understanding desired for the study of this topic.

RESEARCH METHOD

Systematic literature review (SLR) is adopted as the research method for this study. SLR was grounded in Medical Science (Cook, Mulrow, & Haynes, 1997) and adopted in the field of management and entrepreneurship (Tranfield et al., 2003) and in environmental studies (Hossain, 2016). This method was used to provide a framework for identifying the gaps in the literature relevant to scaling social and sustainable initiatives and for synthesizing the existing findings. Systematic reviews improve the quality of the review process and outcome by employing a transparent, reproducible procedure (Danang, Margo, Bambang & Erna, 2019). There are 5 phases to facilitate the literature review process namely planning, search, screening, extraction, and synthesis as well as reporting based on the methodology from Tranfield et al., (2003).

Planning: Researcher undertakes planning in the study to identify the research questions. For this study, the research questions were “What elements of learning-by-doing activities exist in the Entrepreneurship Education among selected Agriculture Vocational Colleges in Malaysia?”, “What levels of *insaniah* value education being learnt among youth-at risk studying at selected Agriculture vocational colleges in Malaysia?” and “What nature of *insaniah* value model can be developed into the Agro-based TVETpreneurship Education Framework?”

Search: The search process for articles related to the research questions was conducted using a search database; Emerald Insights, Proquest Dissertation, Spingerlink, Research Gate, Google Scholar, Sage Pub, Science and Direct Pro Quest. The selection of the articles was based on articles that showed good and appropriate presentations on Social Enterprise, Social Funding Model, Entrepreneurial Intention and related empirical studies. The key words used in

this study are “Entrepreneur; Agriculture Entrepreneur; Agriculture Aspiration; At-Risk Youth; Insaniah Model; Systematic Literature Review”. With these key words, researchers can find answers to research questions from general to specific.

Screening: Search results from search online databases; Emerald Insights, Proquest Dissertation, Spingerlink, Research Gate, Google Scholar, Sage Pub, Science and Direct Pro Quest have produced 1499 articles listed along with abstracts. After that, the researcher re-evaluated the results of the study based on the research questions. Then, the researcher implemented specific acceptance and exclusion techniques to facilitate review of the articles. The acceptance criteria are:

- Only select articles in English and Bahasa Malaysia;
- Sources of articles in research papers, books, pamphlets, webinar videos, thesis reports and articles from websites;
- No duplicate copies;
- Read Abstracts and Keywords that contain explanations of research questions;
- Articles containing empirical and theoretical research methods;
- From various countries.

The exclusion criteria are:

- Articles other than English;
- Articles that do not match the research questions;
- There are duplicate copies.

Extraction: As a result of the screening criteria, researcher has obtained a total of 22 articles from the results of the reception to search for "Aspiration Agriculture" and "Youth & Argiculture" as search techniques in general. Then, the researcher made re-acceptance according to the research questions that had themes for agriculture entrepreneurship, aspiration agriculture and at-risk youth. However, not on the insaniah value in developing agriprenuer are studied in depth. The purpose of the researcher has chosen the keywords of this study generally to look at all the methods as well as the theoretical basis used in the study in general.

From these results, the researcher conducted an in-depth review of the study as outlined in Microsoft Excel as an acceptance database. With the database in Microsoft Excel is very useful for researchers to know and obtain articles in a structured manner and make research reviews in the form of columns in Excel (Tranfield et al., 2003), Through Excel columns, researcher can collect and classify information aspects of articles by Title, Author, Distributor and Year of Publication. The main focus of this study was to find the literature gap in the study results from previous studies on agriculture entrepreneurship, aspiration agriculture and at-risk youth.

Figure 1: Literature search process (adapted from Danang, et al., 2019)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the researchers analyse selected publications from 2000 until 2019. Only 2 articles were published before 2012, and another 20 articles were published in 2012 until 2019, the highest publication in 2018 with 6 articles. Based on a systematic review of agriculture aspiration by Ravi and Swamikannu (2021), Figure 2 indicated that 73% of the reference materials are based on empirical studies. There are 6 studies that use qualitative and theoretical methods. Although qualitative data does not provide reference to the variables in the scaling process of interest, but it can provide useful information for the means and reasons for the use of the scaling process. Most of the empirical studies are based on quantitative research methods which is 16 studies. No case studies were identified. Some 41% of the studies are scored as high quality articles.

Figure 2: Flow diagram of the systematic screening process
(adapted from Ravi & Swamikannu, 2021)

CONCLUSION

A review was made based on publications from selected online databases. Areas such as aspirational agriculture and the learning-by-doing in entrepreneurship education were being studied in number of researches. Limited studies had focused on associating these variables to insaniah value. On the contrary, numerous past researches derived from the western perspectives which concentrating on the agripreneur development and future workforce. Lack of research focusing on developing an insaniah value among learners of agripreneur. This paper aims to explore the extent of learning-by-doing in this agenda of building agripreneurs.

The researchers suggest further exploration of frameworks in specific branches or topics, such as learning-by-doing in agriculture college in terms of entrepreneurship. Exploration in different dimension and relationships in the framework may offer new concept. Comparing results across various branches and topics can potentially yield results that are able to explain the relationships between insaniah value, entrepreneurship and agriculture education. It is also important for future study to explore the sustainability of agriculture entrepreneurs associating funding, management, and the pillar support.

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